

1 **DNA breaks are key contributors to the cost of antibiotic resistance**

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23 **Abstract**

24

25 **Antibiotic resistance often causes a fitness cost to bacteria in drug-free environments. The cost is**
26 **the main determinant of the prevalence of resistances upon reducing antibiotics use.**
27 **Understanding its causes is considered the Holy Grail in the antibiotic resistance field. We show**
28 **that most of the variation in the cost of resistances common in pathogens can be explained by**
29 **DNA breaks, a previously unsuspected cause. We demonstrate that the cost can be manipulated**
30 **by targeting the RNase responsible for degrading R-loops, which cause DNA breaks. Indeed, lack**
31 **of RNase HI drives *Escherichia coli* resistant clones to extinction in populations with high initial**
32 **frequency of resistance. Thus, RNase HI provides a promising target for antimicrobials specific**
33 **against resistant bacteria, which we validate using a repurposed drug. These results show**
34 **previously unknown effects of resistance on bacterial physiology and provide a framework for**
35 **the development of novel strategies against antibiotic resistance.**

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37 **Keywords**

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39 antibiotic resistance; fitness cost; DNA breaks; RNase HI targeting; repurposed drug.

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44 **Introduction**

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46 Antibiotic resistance entails a large human and economic burden worldwide ([Global](#)
47 [antimicrobial resistance surveillance system \(GLASS\) report: Early implementation 2017-2018.](#)
48 [Geneva: World Health Organization. 2018](#)). Its maintenance and spread in bacterial populations
49 depend on the rate at which resistance is acquired and on its effect on bacterial fitness. This effect is
50 typically deleterious, resulting in the so-called cost of resistance. The cost of resistance is influenced by
51 the environment, by interactions between the resistances and the genetic background in which they
52 appear (epistasis), and by subsequent acquisition of mutations compensating for fitness defects
53 (compensatory evolution) ([Durão, Balbontín, & Gordo, 2018](#)). Importantly, the magnitude of the cost is
54 the main biological parameter influencing the fate of resistances upon reducing antibiotic use ([Dan I.](#)
55 [Andersson & Hughes, 2010](#)). Despite its importance, the causes of the cost are far from being
56 completely understood ([Vogwill & MacLean, 2015](#)), and the identification of these causes has become
57 the “Holy Grail” in the antibiotic resistance field.

58

59 Resistance mutations often map to genes encoding proteins targeted by antibiotics. These target
60 proteins are typically involved in essential functions, such as transcription, translation, DNA replication
61 or cell wall biosynthesis. Resistance mutations cause alterations in the structure of the target protein,
62 rendering it insensitive to the drug, but often adversely affecting its function ([Andersson & Levin,](#)
63 [1999, Andersson & Hughes, 2010, Durão, Balbontín, & Gordo, 2018](#)). These pleiotropic effects hold
64 the key to manipulating resistance levels in bacterial populations ([Dan I. Andersson & Hughes, 2010](#)).

65 Rifampicin and streptomycin resistance mutations (Rif^R and Str^R), common in pathogenic bacteria, map
66 to the genes *rpoB* and *rpsL*, encoding the β' subunit of the RNA polymerase and the 30S ribosomal
67 subunit protein S12, respectively. Rif^R and Str^R mutations are representative examples of resistances to
68 antibiotics targeting transcription and translation, respectively. Rif^R mutations show different costs ([Jin](#)
69 [& Gross, 1989](#), [Reynolds, 2000](#)), and these are commonly attributed to alterations in the rates of
70 transcription initiation, elongation, slippage or termination ([Guarente & Beckwith, 1978](#), [Das, Merrill,](#)
71 [& Adhya, 1978](#), [Yanofsky & Horn, 1981](#), [Gowrishankar & Pittard, 1982](#), [Fisher & Yanofsky, 1983](#),
72 [Hammer, Jensen, Poulsen, Oppenheim, & Gottesman, 1987](#), [Jin, Walter, & Gross, 1988](#), [Jin *et al.*,](#)
73 [1988](#), [Jin & Gross, 1989](#), [Jin & Gross, 1991](#), [Zhou & Jin, 1997](#), [Zhou & Jin, 1998](#), [Reynolds, 2000](#),
74 [Zhou *et al.*, 2013](#)). Likewise, most Str^R mutations also cause a cost ([Ruusala, Andersson, Ehrenberg, &](#)
75 [Kurland, 1984](#), [Schrag & Perrot, 1996](#), [Paulander, Maisnier-Patin, & Andersson, 2009](#)), which is
76 currently interpreted via the effects of these mutations on translation fidelity and processivity ([Gorini &](#)
77 [Kataja, 1964](#), [Gartner & Orias, 1966](#), [Ozaki, Mizushima, & Nomura, 1969](#), [Birge & Kurland, 1969](#),
78 [Galas & Branscomb, 1976](#), [McMahon & Landau, 1982](#), [Bohman, Ruusala, Jelenc, & Kurland, 1984](#),
79 [Dong & Kurland, 1995](#), [Schrag & Perrot, 1996](#), [Paulander, Maisnier-Patin, & Andersson, 2009](#)). Thus,
80 at present, the costs of Rif^R and Str^R mutations are thought to be caused by defects in protein synthesis,
81 either at a global cellular level ([Applebee, Herrgård, & Palsson, 2008](#), [Hall, 2013](#), [Qi, Preston, &](#)
82 [MacLean, 2014](#)) or limited to specific functions or regulons ([Zhou & Jin, 1998](#), [Paulander, Maisnier-](#)
83 [Patin, & Andersson, 2009](#), [Ochi & Hosaka, 2013](#), [Pelchovich *et al.*, 2014](#)).

84

85 Motivated by the principle that compensatory evolution would be capable of shedding light on
86 the evolutionary cause of the cost of resistance, we recently showed that the fitness cost of double
87 resistance (Rif^R Str^R) can be reduced via overexpression of *nusG* or *nusE* (Moura de Sousa, Balbontín,
88 Durão, & Gordo, 2017), which encode the proteins that physically connect the RNA polymerase and
89 the ribosome (Burmamann *et al.*, 2010). This suggests that the reduction of the cost can be achieved by
90 reinforcing the coupling between transcription and translation, besides the already known partial
91 recovery in protein biosynthesis (Andersson & Hughes, 2010). Coupling between transcription and
92 translation is known to prevent spontaneous backtracking of the RNA polymerase (Herbert *et al.*, 2010,
93 Proshkin, Rahmouni, Mironov, & Nudler, 2010, Kohler, Mooney, Mills, Landick, & Cramer, 2017,
94 Saxena *et al.*, 2018), which can ultimately cause double-strand DNA breaks (Dutta *et al.*, 2011). This
95 led us to hypothesize that cells carrying different Rif^R and Str^R mutations have higher number of DNA
96 breaks, and it is the DNA breaks that drive their cost.

97

98 In this study, we show that DNA breaks caused by resistance mutations are major contributors to
99 their fitness cost, explaining 73% of its variation across resistant genotypes. The involvement of R-
100 loops in the generation of DNA breaks allowed us to identify RNase HI as an important determinant of
101 the cost of resistance, which we validate using a repurposed drug. We further show that targeting
102 RNase HI is a plausible strategy for the effective elimination of resistant bacteria, as lack of RNase HI
103 favors extinction of resistant clones when competing against sensitive bacteria, abolishing
104 compensatory evolution.

105

106 **Results**

107

108 DNA breaks explain variation in the fitness cost of resistance

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110 In order to test if Rif^R and Str^R mutations generate DNA breaks, and whether DNA breaks drive
111 the cost of resistance, we simultaneously measured competitive fitness and activation of the SOS
112 response (Maslowska, Makiela-Dzvenska, & Fijalkowska, 2019), a well-known proxy for the
113 occurrence of DNA breaks (Quillardet, Huisman, D'Ari, & Hofnung, 1982). We carried out these
114 assays in sensitive *E. coli*, Str^R strains (RpsL^{K43N}, RpsL^{K43T}, and RpsL^{K43R}), Rif^R strains (RpoB^{H526L},
115 RpoB^{H526Y}, and RpoB^{S531F}), and double resistant mutants carrying the nine possible combinations of
116 these resistance alleles. Remarkably, fourteen out of the fifteen resistant strains show increased SOS
117 activation (Figure 1A), demonstrating that resistance mutations indeed cause DNA breaks. Moreover,
118 the SOS induction strongly correlates with the cost of resistance, explaining 73% of its variation
119 (Figure 1B). This suggests that DNA breaks are key contributors to the cost of resistance. To
120 independently confirm the occurrence of DNA breaks in resistant bacteria, we used a system which
121 permits direct visualization of double-stranded DNA ends by fluorescence microscopy (Shee *et al.*,
122 2013). We combined this system with the SOS reporter, and analyzed a subset of resistant mutants and
123 sensitive bacteria. As expected, this corroborated that resistance mutations indeed cause increased
124 number of DNA breaks (Table 1, Figure S1). We then asked if resistance mutations involving a
125 different mechanism which could lead to perturbations of transcription-translation coupling also
126 generate DNA breaks. The commonly used antibiotic erythromycin targets the 50S ribosomal subunit,

127 affecting translation and its coupling with transcription ([Sedlyarova et al., 2017](#)). Erythromycin
128 resistance mutations (Erm^R) mapping to the genes *rplD* and *rplV* (encoding the 50S ribosomal subunit
129 proteins L4 and L22, respectively) are known to reduce translation elongation rate ([Chittum &
130 Champney, 1994](#), [Zaman, Fitzpatrick, Lindahl, & Zengel, 2007](#)), likely affecting transcription-
131 translation coupling. We isolated Erm^R clones carrying either RplD^{G66R} or RplV^{Δ(82-84)} mutations and
132 found that both mutants show increased SOS ([Figure 1C](#)), demonstrating that other resistance
133 mutations, with a different mechanistic basis but affecting the same process (transcription-translation
134 coupling) also cause DNA breaks.

135

136 The cost of resistance can be very reduced when bacteria grow in glucose as the sole carbon
137 source, and specific Rif^R and/or Str^R alleles show no significant cost in such minimal medium
138 ([Paulander, Maisnier-Patin, & Andersson, 2009](#), [Trindade, Sousa, & Gordo, 2012](#), [Durão, Trindade,
139 Sousa, & Gordo, 2015](#)). We therefore reasoned that, if DNA breaks are an important cause of the cost,
140 they should be reduced in an environment where the costs are smaller. In agreement with our
141 hypothesis, resistant mutants show reduced DNA breaks in minimal medium ([Figure 2A](#)), leading to
142 and a weaker correlation between DNA breaks and the cost ([Figure 2B](#)). This further validates DNA
143 breaks as a key predictor of the fitness cost of antibiotic resistance.

144

145 Compensatory evolution cause reduction of DNA breaks

146

147 We then hypothesized that, if DNA breaks are major drivers of the fitness cost of resistance,
148 compensatory evolution of resistant strains should result in a reduction of DNA breaks. To test this, we
149 compared the cost and SOS induction in the RpsL^{K43T} RpoB^{H526Y} double mutant and in an isogenic strain
150 additionally carrying the most prevalent compensatory mutation found in our previous study:
151 RpoC^{Q1126K} (Moura de Sousa *et al.*, 2017). As hypothesized, both cost and SOS induction are greatly
152 reduced in the compensated strain (Figure 3A), confirming that DNA breaks are targeted by
153 compensatory evolution. In order to test if this is general, we analyzed nine compensated clones from
154 three independent populations of the RpsL^{K43T} RpoB^{H526Y} double mutant propagated for fifteen days in
155 the absence of antibiotics. As expected, the costs are smaller in the evolved strains and, as
156 hypothesized, all the nine compensated clones show decreased SOS induction compared to their
157 resistant ancestor (Figure 3B). This demonstrates that compensatory evolution widely targets
158 mechanisms that reduce DNA breaks and further reinforces the notion that DNA breaks are major
159 contributors to the cost of antibiotic resistance.

160

161 RNAse HI strongly influences the fitness of resistant bacteria

162

163 Transcription-translation uncoupling leads to increased formation of R-loops, which cause DNA
164 breaks (Dutta *et al.*, 2011). We thus reasoned that the increased number of DNA breaks in the resistant
165 mutants could also involve R-loops. In this scenario, deleting RNase HI, which specifically degrades
166 R-loops (Tadokoro & Kanaya, 2009), should lead to increased DNA breaks and greater costs of Rif^R
167 and Str^R. Accordingly, both DNA breaks and the cost of resistance are greatly exacerbated in the $\Delta rnhA$

168 background (Figure 4A, Table 1, Figure S2, Figure S3A). Conversely, mild overproduction of RNase
169 HI can ameliorate both phenotypes in a subset of mutants (Figure S4); however, strong overproduction
170 is toxic for the cell (Stockum, Lloyd, & Rudolph, 2012, Wimberly *et al.*, 2013), irrespectively of its
171 genotype (Figure S5). These results confirm the involvement of R-loops in the uncoupling-mediated
172 production of DNA breaks caused by resistance and suggest that RNase HI can be a target for
173 manipulating the fitness of resistant strains.

174

175 RNase HI can serve as a target specific against resistant bacteria

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177 We then asked whether targeting RNase HI function could be used to select specifically against
178 resistant bacteria in polymorphic populations with high frequency of resistance. RNase HI inhibitors
179 are currently studied as antiretrovirals (Tramontano, Corona, & Menendez-Arias, 2019). A
180 commercially available one, RHI001, has been shown to inhibit the activity of purified *E. coli* RNase
181 HI protein *in vitro* (Kim *et al.*, 2013). In competitions between sensitive and resistant bacteria, we
182 observed that addition of RHI001 to the medium increases the cost of most resistant mutants (Figure
183 4B), on average by 14%. RHI001 also reduces fitness of double resistant bacteria more than that of
184 sensitive bacteria in the absence of competition (Figures S3B and S3C). Chemical inhibition was not as
185 effective as genetic removal (which increases cost on average by 28%) (Figure 4C and D), as may be
186 expected, since stability, diffusibility across the bacterial envelope, pharmacokinetics and
187 pharmacodynamics of RHI001 *in vivo* are unknown, and potentially suboptimal. Nevertheless, these
188 results suggest that inhibiting RNase HI may be a plausible strategy to select specifically against

189 resistant strains coexisting with sensitive bacteria, as long as resistant strains fail to evolve adaptations
190 that abrogate their extinction. In order to test this hypothesis, we propagated a mixture of sensitive
191 bacteria (CFP-labeled) competing against a pool of five single resistant mutants (YFP-labeled
192 RpsL^{K43N}, RpsL^{K43T}, RpoB^{H526L}, RpoB^{H526Y}, and RpoB^{S531F}) during 15 days, in the absence of antibiotics.
193 We studied the frequency dynamics of resistant clones under both strong bottlenecks (1:1500
194 dilutions), where new adaptive mutations are less likely to spread, and weak bottlenecks (1:50
195 dilutions), where propagation of adapted clones is more probable. In parallel, we performed identical
196 propagations, but in which all strains lack RNase HI, as a proxy for optimal inhibition of RNase HI
197 function. We observed that, in the presence of RNase HI, sensitive bacteria initially outcompete
198 resistant clones but, as the propagation progresses, resistant bacteria increase in frequency - likely due
199 to compensatory evolution - finally reaching coexistence (Figure 5A, blue lines). Remarkably, in the
200 propagations of strains lacking RNase HI, resistant bacteria were completely outcompeted and went
201 extinct by day seven (Figure 5A, red lines), even under mild bottlenecks (Figure 5B). Altogether, these
202 results show that targeting RNase HI is a promising strategy to selectively eliminate resistant bacteria.

203

204 Discussion

205

206 We show that mutations known to affect protein synthesis generate DNA breaks, which explain
207 73% of the variation in their cost (Figure 1, Table 1, Figure S1). Compensatory evolution indicates that
208 these resistances cause uncoupling between transcription and translation (Moura de Sousa *et al.*, 2017),
209 which can result in DNA breaks (Dutta, Shatalin, Epshtein, Gottesman, & Nudler, 2011). Indeed, we

210 show that the RpsL^{K43N} RpoB^{H526Y} and RpsL^{K43T} RpoB^{H526Y} double mutants, which combine alleles that
211 cause increased transcription elongation rate (Fisher & Yanofsky, 1983) and decreased translation rate
212 (Schrag & Perrot, 1996, Hosaka *et al.*, 2004), show the highest costs and DNA breaks (Figure 1).
213 Curiously, inhibition of translation has been shown to alleviate the cost of Rif^R mutations in
214 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Alex R. Hall, Iles, & MacLean, 2011). In light of the results presented here,
215 this observation is compatible with a scenario in which Rif^R mutations cause a perturbation of
216 transcription-translation coupling by virtue of reduced RNA polymerase processivity, and translation
217 inhibitors promote re-coupling by decreasing ribosomal activity. In agreement with the notion of single
218 resistance mutations causing significant uncoupling, single Rif^R or Str^R mutations with high cost
219 (Trindade *et al.*, 2009) cause a strong induction of the SOS response (Figure S6A). We also showed
220 that RNase HI is a key determinant of the fitness of resistant mutants (Figure 4, Table 1, Figure S3A,
221 Figure S4). Interestingly, transcription-translation uncoupling caused by chemical inhibition of
222 translation can generate R-loops (Broccoli *et al.*, 2004, Dutta, Shatalin, Epshtein, Gottesman, &
223 Nudler, 2011, Negro *et al.*, 2019). Thus, perturbations of the coupling between transcription and
224 translation increases the requirement of RNase HI function by bacteria. This opens the possibility to
225 designing novel therapeutic interventions by combining drugs targeting transcription or translation with
226 RNase HI inhibitors in order to increase DNA breaks and costs of resistance, therefore enhancing the
227 effectiveness of antimicrobial treatments.

228

229 DNA breaks induced by transcription-translation uncoupling involve increased replication-
230 transcription conflicts (Dutta *et al.*, 2011), which have been shown to cause both R-loops (Lang *et al.*,

231 2017) and DNA breaks (Merrikh *et al.*, 2012). We observed more DNA breaks in rich than in minimal
232 media (Figure 1A, Figure 2A). This might be linked to the fact that replication-transcription conflicts
233 are maximized during fast replication (Merrikh, Machón, Grainger, Grossman, & Soutanas, 2011), and
234 bacteria replicate faster in rich than in minimal media (C. H. Wang & Koch, 1978) (Figure S6B).
235 Supporting this notion, we observed that, in rich medium, the costs are detected in the first 4 hours,
236 when cells are growing exponentially, while resistant bacteria can even show advantage when growth
237 slows down (Figure S6C). Consistent with this observation, resistant mutants have been shown to
238 outcompete sensitive bacteria in aging colonies (Wrande, Roth, & Hughes, 2008, Katz & Hershberg,
239 2013). Another interesting fact is that stable DNA replication (initiation of DNA replication at sites
240 different from *OriC*) can be induced by lack of RNase HI or conditions that activate SOS (Kogoma,
241 1997). Thus, Rif^R and Str^R mutations, which induce SOS, could favor replication-transcription conflicts
242 via induction of stable DNA replication. This can generate a feed-forward loop of synergistic
243 deleterious effects, which may be further enhanced by the downregulation of *rnhA* caused by the
244 induction of the SOS response (Quiñones, Kücherer, Piechocki, & Messer, 1987). This detrimental
245 runaway loop and the environmental effects on the cost described above could potentially be exploited
246 therapeutically, via concurrent chemical and dietary treatments designed to maximize the cost of
247 resistance.

248

249 We revealed RNase HI as a promising target specific against resistant bacteria (Figure 4), and
250 showed that lack of RNase HI favors extinction of resistant clones, preventing compensatory evolution
251 (Figure 5). This is specially important for resistances mediated by mutations (Hershberg, 2017) or for

252 pathogens that acquire antibiotic resistance exclusively through mutation, such as *Mycobacterium*
253 *tuberculosis*, which often carries Rif^R and Str^R mutations (Almeida Da Silva & Palomino, 2011).
254 Interestingly, RNase HI has been proposed as an antimycobacterial target due to its essentiality in
255 *Mycobacterium smegmatis* (Minias *et al.*, 2015, Gupta, Chatterjee, Glickman, & Shuman, 2017). The
256 results presented here support the plausibility of this strategy.

257

258 An understanding of the determinants of maintenance and dissemination of antibiotic resistance,
259 such as its cost, is urgently needed ([Global antimicrobial resistance surveillance system \(GLASS\)
260 report: Early implementation 2017-2018. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2018](#)). We show that
261 DNA breaks drive the cost of resistance and reveal RNase HI as a promising antimicrobial target
262 specific against resistant bacteria, which we validated using a repurposed drug. Overall, our results
263 uncover important effects of resistances on bacterial physiology and demonstrate the plausibility of
264 exploiting these effects to develop novel strategies against antibiotic resistance.

265

266 **Materials and methods**

267

268 Bacterial strains, media and growth conditions

269

270 All the strains used in this study (Data S1) derive from strains RB266, RB323 or RB324, which
271 are derivatives of *E. coli* K12 MG1655 (Blattner *et al.*, 1997). Fluorescently labeled strains harbor a
272 copy of either YFP or CFP under the control of the lac-regulated promoter P_{LacO-1} inserted either in the

273 *yzgL* pseudogene locus or in the *galK* gene, a deletion comprising the entire *lac* operon (to make
274 constitutive the expression of the fluorescent proteins), and the SOS reporter construction P_{sulA} -
275 *mCherry* inserted in the *ysaCD* pseudogene locus. The SOS reporter fusion was constructed by
276 replacing a *tetA-sacB* selectable/counterselectable marker (Li, Thomason, Sawitzke, Costantino, &
277 Court, 2013) located upstream from a *mCherry-FRT-aph-FRT* cassette previously inserted in the
278 *ysaCD* locus by the regulatory regions (150bp upstream from the translation initiation site) of the SOS-
279 regulated gene *sulA*. Resistant mutants additionally carry different chromosomal alleles conferring
280 antibiotic resistance/s. The fluorescent constructions were generated by Lambda-Red recombineering
281 (Murphy, Campellone, & Poteete, 2000, Yu *et al.*, 2000, Datsenko & Wanner, 2000), followed by
282 transference to a clean background by P1 transduction (Lennox, 1955), and subsequent transduction of
283 the resistance alleles. The clean deletion of *rnhA* was constructed by markerless recombineering using
284 a *tetR-P_{tet}-ccdB-cat* selection/counterselection cassette as described in Figueroa-Bossi & Bossi
285 (Figueroa-Bossi & Bossi, 2015), and subsequent transfer of the markerless deletion to a clean
286 background by P1 transduction, using as recipient an isogenic strain carrying a deletion of the nearby
287 gene *proB*, which causes proline auxotrophy, and selecting for growth in minimal medium. The
288 presence of each construction/mutation was assessed by PCR-mediated amplification of the
289 corresponding region and Sanger sequencing. The Gam-GFP construction (Shee *et al.*, 2013) was
290 generously contributed by Professor Susan M. Rosenberg. The chromosomal construction comprising a
291 copy of the *rnhA* gene under the control of a promoter inducible by arabinose (Stockum *et al.*, 2012)
292 was kindly donated by Dr. Christian J. Rudolph. Derivatives of these strains carrying the P_{sulA} -*mCherry*
293 and different resistance mutations were constructed by P1 transduction. The plasmid pRB-5 (carrying

294 the *rnhA* gene under the control of a promoter inducible by anhydrotetracycline) was constructed by
295 PCR amplification of the vector pZS*11 (Subramaniam, Pan, & Cluzel, 2013) and the construction
296 *tetR-P_{LtetO-1}-rnhA* from strain RB1207, subsequent restriction with AatII and HindIII enzymes, ligation
297 and electroporation. The construction *tetR-P_{LtetO-1}-rnhA* in strain RB1207 was made by Lambda-Red
298 recombineering (Murphy, Campellone, & Poteete, 2000, Yu *et al.*, 2000, Datsenko & Wanner, 2000),
299 and selection/countersélection (Li *et al.*, 2013), over a previous *P_{LtetO-1}-sfGFP* construction (Balbontín,
300 Vlamakis, & Kolter, 2014). Cultures were grown in either Lysogeny Broth (LB, Miller formulation)
301 (Bertani, 1951) or M9 broth supplemented with 0.4% glucose (Maniatis *et al. Molecular cloning: A*
302 *laboratory manual (CSHL Press)*), in round-bottom 96-well plates incubated at 37°C with shaking (700
303 r.p.m.) in a Grant-bio PHMP-4 benchtop incubator, unless indicated otherwise. Solid medium was LB
304 containing 1.5% agar, supplemented when necessary with antibiotics at the following concentrations:
305 rifampicin (100 µg/ml), streptomycin (100 µg/ml), ampicillin (100 µg/ml), erythromycin (150 µg/ml),
306 kanamycin (100 µg/ml), chloramphenicol (25 µg/ml).

307

308 Competitive fitness/SOS induction assays

309

310 The relative fitness (selection coefficient per generation) of each YFP-tagged resistant strain
311 carrying the SOS reporter was measured by competitive growth against an isogenic sensitive strain *E.*
312 *coli* K12 MG1655 constitutively expressing CFP and also carrying the SOS reporter. The formula used
313 to calculate the selection coefficient was $s = \left[\ln(NRf/NSf) - \ln(NRi/NSi) \right] / \ln(NSf/NSi)$, being **NRi** and

314 *NRf* the initial and final number of resistant bacteria, and *NSi* and *NSf* the initial and final number of
315 sensitive bacteria. The competitor strains were first streaked out of their respective frozen vials, then
316 individual colonies were inoculated separately in medium without antibiotics and incubated overnight
317 (approximately 16h); the next morning, the number of cells in each culture was measured by Flow
318 Cytometry, and 10 μ l of 1:1 mixtures of YFP and CFP bacteria were added to 140 μ l of medium, at an
319 initial number of approximately 10^6 cells. The initial and final frequencies of the strains were obtained
320 by counting their cell numbers in the Flow Cytometer. Generation time was estimated from the
321 doubling time of the reference strain (approximately five generations at 4h, and approximately eight
322 generations at 24h), and the selection coefficient was determined as described above for each
323 independent competition. The proportion of SOS-induced bacteria was quantified as the number of
324 either YFP-tagged or CFP-labeled bacteria showing red fluorescence (from the *P_{sulA}-mCherry* SOS
325 reporter fusion) above a threshold determined by the fluorescence levels of the control strains *lexA*
326 (*ind-*) (constitutive repression of the SOS response) and Δ *lexA* (constitutive activation of the SOS
327 response) ([Lin & Little, 1988](#)). The data represented is the induction level of each mutant normalized
328 with respect to the induction levels of the sensitive it is competing against. In the competitions
329 including the RNase HI inhibitor 2-[[[3-Bromo-5-(2-furanyl)-7-(trifluoromethyl)pyrazolo[1,5-
330 a]pyrimidin-2-yl]carbonyl]amino]-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-benzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester
331 (RHI001), the medium was supplemented with 500 μ M of RHI001 (Glxxx Laboratories Inc., catalog
332 number GLXC-03982).

333

334 Flow Cytometry

335

336 A BD LSR Fortessa™ SORP flow cytometer was used to quantify bacteria, using a 96-well plate
337 High-Throughput Sampler (HTS) and SPHERO fluorescent spheres (AccuCount 2.0 µm blank
338 particles), in order to accurately measure volumes. Bacterial numbers were calculated based on the
339 counts of fluorescently labeled bacteria with respect the known number of beads added to a given
340 volume. The instrument was equipped with a 488 nm laser used for scatter parameters and YFP
341 detection, a 442 nm laser for CFP detection and a 561 nm laser for mCherry detection. Relative to
342 optical configuration, CFP, YPF and mCherry were measured using bandpass filters in the range of
343 470/20 nm, 540/30 nm and 630/75nm, respectively. The analyzer is also equipped with a forward
344 scatter (FSC) detector in a photomultiplier tube (PMT) to detect bacteria. The samples were acquired
345 using FACSDiVa (version 6.2) software, and analyzed using FlowJo (version X 10.0.7r2). All Flow
346 Cytometry experiments were performed at the Flow Cytometry Facility of Instituto Gulbenkian de
347 Ciência, Oeiras, Portugal.

348

349 Selection for Erm^R bacteria

350

351 Fifteen independent colonies of sensitive bacteria were separately inoculated in LB in a 96-well
352 plate, incubated at at 37°C with shaking (700 r.p.m) for 7 hours, and 0.1ml of either independent
353 culture was plated onto a LB agar plate supplemented with 150 µg/ml erythromycin, and incubated at
354 37°C for 5 days (Erm^R strains grow in the presence of erythromycin, albeit slowly). Colonies able to
355 grow in these plates were streaked onto plates supplemented with 150 µg/ml erythromycin, in order to

356 further assess their *bona fide* resistance, and the *rplD*, and *rplV* genes of the resistant clones were
357 amplified by PCR and analyzed by Sanger sequencing.

358

359 Microscopy

360

361 Early exponential cultures were diluted into pre-warmed medium containing the inducer of the
362 Gam-GFP construction (anhydrotetracycline, 25ng/ml) and incubated at 37°C with shaking (240 r.p.m.)
363 for 3h, prior to imaging. Bacterial solutions were then placed onto 1% agarose (in 1X PBS) pads
364 mounted in adhesive frames between the microscope slide and a coverglass. Images were acquired on
365 an Applied Precision DeltavisionCORE system, mounted on an Olympus IX71 inverted microscope,
366 coupled to a Cascade II 1024x1024 EM-CCD camera, using an Olympus 100x 1.4NA Uplan SAPO Oil
367 immersion objective, where GFP and mCherry were imaged with FITC (Ex: 475/28, EM: 528/38) and
368 TRITC (Ex: 542/28, Em: 617/73) fluorescence filtersets, respectively, and DIC optics. Images were
369 deconvoluted with Applied Precision's softWorx software, and prepared for presentation (cropping
370 smaller fields to facilitate visualization, and false-coloring green and red fluorescent signals) using
371 Fiji/ImageJ.

372

373 Long-term propagations of polymorphic populations

374

375 The CFP-tagged sensitive (either WT or *ΔrnhA*) and the five YFP-labeled resistant bacterial
376 (either RpsL^{K43N}, RpsL^{K43T}, RpoB^{H526L}, RpoB^{H526Y}, and RpoB^{S531F} or *ΔrnhA* RpsL^{K43N}, *ΔrnhA* RpsL^{K43T},
377 *ΔrnhA* RpoB^{H526L}, *ΔrnhA* RpoB^{H526Y}, and *ΔrnhA* RpoB^{S531F}) were streaked individually onto LB agar
378 plates and incubated overnight at 37°C. The next day, three independent colonies from each strain were
379 inoculated separately in LB broth (150 μl per well) in a 96-well plate and incubated overnight at 37°C
380 with shaking (700 r.p.m). The next day, bacteria were quantified by Flow Cytometry, and 10 μl of
381 1:1:1:1:1 mixtures of the sensitive and either resistant bacteria were added to 140 μl of medium, at a
382 initial number of approximately 10⁶ cells. The initial frequencies of the fluorescent strains were
383 confirmed by Flow Cytometry. Every 24h, during 15 days, 10 μl of bacteria culture was diluted by a
384 factor of 10⁻², then transferred to 140 μl fresh LB and allowed to grow for additional 24h, reaching
385 approximately 10⁹ cells/ml. In parallel, cell numbers were counted using the Flow Cytometer, in order
386 to measure the frequency of each strain in the mixed population during the experiment, by collecting a
387 sample (10 μl) from the spent culture each day.

388

389 Growth curves

390

391 YFP-tagged sensitive and RpsL^{K43N} RpoB^{H526Y} strains were streaked individually onto LB agar
392 plates and incubated overnight at 37°C. The next day, three independent colonies from each strain were
393 inoculated separately in LB broth (150 μl per well) in a 96-well plate and incubated overnight at 37°C
394 with shaking (700 r.p.m). The next day, bacteria were quantified by Flow Cytometry, and
395 approximately 5x10⁵ bacteria were inoculated in 100-well plates containing LB broth supplemented

396 with either 0.5% DMSO (the solvent of RHI001) or 50 μ M RHI001 (150 μ l per well), and incubated at
397 37°C with continuous shaking (medium amplitude, duration 5s, 10s interval, and stopping 5s before
398 each measurement) in a Bioscreen C (Oy Growth Curves Ab Ltd.) benchtop plate reader, measuring
399 OD₆₀₀ every 30 minutes during 12h.

400

401 Statistical analyses

402

403 All analyses were conducted using Libreoffice Calc version 5.4.1.2 (www.libreoffice.org)
404 software, R version 3.4.4 (www.r-project.org) software via RStudio version 1.1.442 interface
405 (www.rstudio.com) and GraphPad Prism version 7.04 (www.graphpad.com). For each set of
406 competitions ($n \geq 3$), two-tailed unpaired Student's *t*-tests were used. For testing the association between
407 the fitness cost and the level of SOS induction, a linear regression of the *s* with the logarithm of the
408 fold change in SOS induction of each resistant clone (with respect to the sensitive bacteria it is
409 competing against in the same well), was used.

410

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412

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424

425 **Author contributions**

426

427 R.B: conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology,
428 visualization, writing – original draft. I.G: conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition,
429 methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, writing – review & editing.

430

431 **Competing interests**

432

433 The authors declare no competing interests.

434

435 **Data availability**

436

437 All the strains used ([Data S1](#)) are available via Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). The raw
438 data of the experiments shown in all figures and the table are available in [Data S2](#). The images
439 analyzed to obtain the data shown in [Table 1](#), and those used in [Figures S1](#) and [S2](#) are available in the
440 public data repository Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3381746).

441

442 **References**

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445 **Figure 1. DNA breaks explain variation in the fitness cost of resistance.** **A.** Fitness cost (red bars) and SOS
 446 induction (blue bars) of sensitive bacteria and Str^R and Rif^R mutants in LB broth at 4 hours. The strains are
 447 ordered from lower to higher fitness cost (top to bottom). The dashed line indicates no SOS induction. Error
 448 bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of independent biological replicates ($n \geq 5$). N.S. non-significant; * $P <$
 449 0.05; ** $P <$ 0.01; *** $P <$ 0.001; **** $P <$ 0.0001 (two-tailed Student's t test). **B.** Correlation between the fitness
 450 cost (y axis) and the SOS induction (x axis) representing all the data points from A. The blue line represents the
 451 logarithmic regression line, and the grey area represents the 95% confidence interval. **C.** SOS induction (blue
 452 bars) and fitness cost (red bars) of sensitive bacteria and Erm^R mutants in LB broth at 4 hours. The dashed line
 453 indicates no SOS induction. Error bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of independent biological replicates
 454 ($n=6$). N.S. non-significant; * $P <$ 0.05; ** $P <$ 0.01; *** $P <$ 0.001; **** $P <$ 0.0001 (two-tailed Student's t test).

455 **Figure 2. DNA breaks are reduced in minimal medium.** **A.** Fitness cost (red bars), and SOS induction (blue
456 bars) of sensitive bacteria and Str^R and/or Rif^R mutants in minimal medium at 8 hours. The strains are ordered
457 from lower to higher cost (top to bottom). The dashed line indicates no SOS induction. Error bars represent
458 mean \pm standard deviation of independent biological replicates (n=6). N.S. non-significant; * $P < 0.05$; ** $P <$
459 0.01 ; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's t test). **B.** Correlation between the fitness cost (y axis)
460 and the SOS induction (x axis) representing all the data points from panel A. The blue line represents the
461 logarithmic regression line, and the grey area represents the 95% confidence interval.

462 **Figure 3. Compensatory evolution cause reduction of DNA breaks.** **A.** SOS induction (blue bars) and fitness
 463 cost (red bars), of sensitive (left) double resistant (center) and double resistant carrying a compensatory mutation
 464 (right) bacteria in LB broth at 4 hours. The dashed line indicates no SOS induction. Error bars represent mean \pm
 465 standard deviation of independent biological replicates ($n \geq 3$). N.S. non-significant; $*P < 0.05$; $**P < 0.01$; $***P$
 466 < 0.001 ; $****P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's t test). **B.** Fitness cost (red bars), and SOS induction (blue bars)
 467 of sensitive, ancestral RpsL^{K43T} RpoB^{H526Y} and nine compensated RpsL^{K43T} RpoB^{H526Y} clones in LB broth at 4
 468 hours. The black dashed line indicates no SOS induction. The grey dashed lines mark the cost/SOS of the
 469 ancestral double mutant. Error bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of independent biological replicates
 470 ($n \geq 3$). N.S. non-significant; $*P < 0.05$; $**P < 0.01$; $***P < 0.001$; $****P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's t test).

472 **Figure 4. RNase HI strongly influences the fitness of resistant bacteria.** **A.** Correlation between the fitness
 473 cost of resistance mutations in wild-type (y axis) or $\Delta rnhA$ backgrounds (x axis). **B.** Correlation between the
 474 fitness cost of resistance mutations in the absence of the RNase HI inhibitor (y axis) or in its presence (x axis).
 475 **C.** Correlation between the fitness cost of resistance mutations in the presence of the RHI001 (y axis) or in the
 476 $\Delta rnhA$ background (x axis). The values corresponding to the wild-type background in panel A and to absence of
 477 RHI001 in panel B are those shown in Figure 1A. Error bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of independent
 478 biological replicates (n \geq 3). The black line in panels A-C represents the linear regression if the costs were
 479 identical **D.** Fitness cost of sensitive bacteria and Str^R and/or Rif^R mutants in the presence of the RNase HI
 480 inhibitor RHI001 (red bars). For comparison, the corresponding values in the absence of the inhibitor (data from
 481 the experiments shown in Figure 1A) or in a $\Delta rnhA$ background (data from the experiments shown in panel A
 482 and Figure S3A) are represented as white and black bars, respectively. Error bars represent mean \pm standard
 483 deviation of independent biological replicates (n=3). N.S. non-significant; * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$;
 484 **** $P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's t test). See also Figures S3, S4 and S5.

A

485 **Figure 5. Lack of RNase HI favors outcompetition of resistant mutants by sensitive bacteria.** Frequency of
 486 single resistant mutants during three independent long-term competitions against sensitive bacteria either in a
 487 genetic background including RNase HI (blue lines) or in a $\Delta rnhA$ background (red lines), imposing either a
 488 strong (1:1500 dilutions) (A) or a mild (1:50 dilutions) (B) bottlenecks.

489 **Tables**

490

491 **Table 1. Percentage of cells showing DNA breaks (Gam-GFP foci) in sensitive and resistant bacteria either**
492 **in wild-type or $\Delta rnhA$ backgrounds.** Except in the Δdam positive control (in which over 100 cells sufficed to
493 provide an illustrative example), at least 1000 cells per group were analyzed. See also Figures S1 and S2.

494

Δdam (positive control)	21.28%
Sensitive	0.72%
<i>rpsL</i> (K43N)	0.73%
<i>rpoB</i> (H526Y)	0.96%
<i>rpsL</i> (K43N) <i>rpoB</i> (H526Y)	10.71%
$\Delta rnhA$ (sensitive)	9.27%
$\Delta rnhA$ <i>rpsL</i> (K43N)	33.92%
$\Delta rnhA$ <i>rpoB</i> (H526Y)	10.02%
$\Delta rnhA$ <i>rpsL</i> (K43N) <i>rpoB</i> (H526Y)	49.90%

495

497 **Figure S1. Visualization of DNA breaks and SOS induction of sensitive, single and double resistant strains**
 498 **by epifluorescence microscopy.** Bacterial cells show a disperse faint green fluorescence distributed along the
 499 cytoplasm, unless DNA breaks are present; upon generation of DNA breaks, the disperse fluorescence
 500 concentrates in bright fluorescent foci (central panels, false-colored in green). Red fluorescence (bottom panels,
 501 false-colored in red) is absent until the SOS response is induced due to the presence of DNA breaks. Cell
 502 elongation (top panels) is a well-known phenotype derived from the inhibition of cell division by SOS-regulated
 503 proteins.

ΔrnhA

504 **Figure S2. Visualization of DNA breaks and SOS induction of sensitive, single and double resistant strains**
505 **in *ΔrnhA* background by epifluorescence microscopy.** Bacterial cells show a disperse faint green fluorescence
506 distributed along the cytoplasm, unless DNA breaks are present; upon generation of DNA breaks, the disperse
507 fluorescence concentrates in bright fluorescent foci (central panels, false-colored in green). Red fluorescence
508 (bottom panels, false-colored in red) is absent until the SOS response is induced due to the presence of DNA
509 breaks. Cell elongation (top panels) is a well known phenotype derived from the inhibition of cell division by
510 SOS-regulated proteins.

511 **Figure S3. Depletion of RNase HI increases fitness cost and SOS induction.** **A.** SOS induction (blue bars)
 512 and fitness cost (red bars), of sensitive bacteria and Str^R and/or Rif^R mutants (labels represent the corresponding
 513 allele/s) in a *Arnha* background. The white bars represent the corresponding values in bacteria with an intact
 514 *rnhA* gene (data from the experiments shown in Figure 1A), for comparison. Error bars represent mean \pm
 515 standard deviation of independent biological replicates (n=6). N.S. non-significant; * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** P
 516 < 0.001 ; **** $P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's *t* test). **B.** Growth curves of RpsL^{K43N} RpoB^{H526Y} double mutant in
 517 the presence of either DMSO (blue lines) or RHI001 (orange lines). Points and error bars represent mean \pm
 518 standard deviation of independent biological replicates (n=3). **C.** Growth curves of sensitive bacteria in the
 519 presence of either DMSO (blue lines) or RHI001 (orange lines). Points and error bars represent mean \pm standard
 520 deviation of independent biological replicates (n=3).

A

521 **Figure S4. Mild overproduction of RNase HI can ameliorate both cost and SOS induction.** SOS induction
 522 (top) and fitness cost (bottom), of sensitive bacteria (left), two single resistant mutants (center) and the double
 523 mutant combining these two alleles (right) in LB broth at 4h (**A**) or 24h (**B**) in a background harboring an
 524 additional chromosomal copy of the gene encoding the RNase HI (*rnhA*) under the control of the arabinose
 525 promoter, either in the absence (red bars) or the presence (white bars) of arabinose. Error bars represent mean ±
 526 standard deviation of independent biological replicates (n=3). N.S. non-significant; * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** P
 527 < 0.001 ; **** $P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's *t* test).

528 **Figure S5. Strong overproduction of RNase HI increases cost and SOS induction in all the backgrounds.**
 529 SOS induction (top) and fitness cost (bottom), of sensitive bacteria (left), two single resistant mutants (center)
 530 and the double mutant combining these two alleles (right) in LB broth at 4h (A) or 24h (B) in a background
 531 harboring a plasmid carrying a copy of the RNase HI gene (*rnhA*) under the control of a promoter inducible by
 532 anhydrotetracycline, either in the absence (white bars) or the presence of different concentrations of the inducer
 533 (greyscale, from light grey to black bars). Error bars represent mean \pm standard deviation of independent
 534 biological replicates ($n \geq 2$). N.S. non-significant; * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$ (two-
 535 tailed Student's *t* test).

536 **Figure S6. A. Costly single mutants show increased SOS induction.** SOS induction (blue bars) and fitness
 537 cost (red bars), of sensitive bacteria (left) and two costly single resistant mutants (center and right). Error bars
 538 represent mean \pm standard deviation of independent biological replicates ($n=3$). N.S. non-significant; * $P < 0.05$;
 539 ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$ (two-tailed Student's t test). **B. Schematic representation of multi-
 540 fork DNA replication of *E. coli* during fast (left) or slow (right) growth.** Black dots represent the origin of
 541 replication, and red lines represent transcription forks; green arrows mark regions of potential conflicts between
 542 replication and transcription forks. **C. Costs are expressed during fast growth.** Data from the experiments
 543 shown in Figure 1A. Left panel: correlation between the fitness cost between time 0 and 4h (y axis) and between
 544 time 0 and 24h (y axis), in LB broth. Right panel: correlation between the fitness cost between time 0 and 4h (y
 545 axis) and between time 4h and 24h (y axis), in LB broth. Black lines represent the linear regressions if the costs
 546 were identical. Blue lines represent the regression lines, and the grey areas represent the 95% confidence
 547 intervals.